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Acceleration of Statistical Sampling with Application to Machine Learning

by

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Abstract

Statistical sampling and optimisation can be very challenging when the landscape is ill-conditioned. In this thesis, we study the potential for thermodynamics-based approaches to overcome the ill-conditioning problem. In particular, we present a preconditioned thermodynamic method which rescales the landscape through a mass preconditioning matrix (referred to here as “MassBAO”). Numerical experiments show that MassBAO improves sampling efficiency in inference problems. Additionally, we propose a preconditioned adaptive Langevin dynamics (PAL) algorithm for optimisation in high-dimensional landscapes, in particular, training deep neural networks. We present PAL as a thermodynamic alternative to the adaptive learning rate method (AdaDelta).

We compare the performance of PAL with the state-of-the-art optimisation algorithms for neural networks on synthetic spiral data and a challenging task of protein conformational state classification using Bovine pancreatic trypsin inhibitor (BTPI) data. We observe that optimisation methods such as Adam overfit to the training data while PAL achieves better performance and avoids overfitting.

Moreover, we introduce a diffusion estimate to analyse optimisation schemes in high-dimensional settings, and show that it is a powerful tool to understand and explain phenomena in training deep neural networks.

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Own Work Declaration

I declare that this thesis has been composed solely by myself and that it has not been submitted, in whole or in part, in any previous application for a degree. Except where stated otherwise by reference or acknowledgment, the work presented is entirely my own.

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1 Introduction

In many branches of science, statistical methods play a vital role in analysing experiments, understanding phenomena and scientific discovery. For instance, the empirical confirmation of the Higgs Boson (which resulted in the award of the 2013 Nobel Prize for Physics) was based on data collection by seven particle detector experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and on the use of statistical inference methods for hypothesis testing [63]. In the field of artificial intelligence and pattern recognition, scientists employ various statistical modelling techniques to draw inferences regarding the underlying system[6]. In the fields of genetics, bioinformatics and computational system biology, Bayesian statistics has become a common statistical framework. For examples, in population genetics, Bayesian methods makes it possible to assign individuals to their population of origin [2], in genomics sequence analysis, Bayesian sampling is at the heart of computational software such as GeneMark [7]. In all these examples, Bayesian statistics is an effective and practical methodology to perform statistical analysis.

In this thesis we apply ideas from Bayesian analysis to design methods for high-dimensional inference and optimisation.

1.1 Bayesian sampling

In Bayesian data analysis, we typically start from a statistical model, termed the *likelihood* which depends on certain parameters, and we assume a *prior* distribution which models one's a priori belief regarding the target quantities of interest before any observations have been considered. **Bayes' Theorem** then allows us to find a conditional distribution of the unknown parameters of the model given the observations. It is calculated using the prior and likelihood functions as follows:

$$p(\theta|y) = \frac{p(y|\theta)p_0(\theta)}{p(y)}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $p(\cdot)$ denote the probability density, and $p(\cdot|y)$ is conditional probability density. The observational data are represented by y and the parameters of statistical model are denoted by θ . The *posterior* density ($p(\theta|y)$) (updated belief about the unknowns), is computed by combining the *prior* density $p_0(\theta)$ with *likelihood* $p(y|\theta)$. $p(y)$ denotes a *normalizing constant* which is the probability of producing the data and can be omitted if samples are equally likely. The Bayesian approach is a way to evaluate fitness of unknown parameters (θ), over repeated sampling from posterior distribution $p(\theta|y)$ for a given observations (y).

In the Bayesian paradigm, the *predictive distribution* allows us to make a prediction for any quantity z based on the model parameters θ and sampling density $p(z|\theta)$ as follows:

$$p(z|y) \propto \int p(z|\theta)p(\theta|y)d\theta, \quad (1.2)$$

where y and z are conditionally independent given the parameters θ .

Bayesian approaches involve practical challenges. The main challenges of Bayesian approaches are the choice of an appropriate prior distribution and computational demands in high-dimensional problems. Using Bayesian analysis involves the evaluation of posterior distribution as a basis for inference. In complex models where the posterior distributions are multivariate or of complex form, analytical solutions can be infeasible. Various numerical integration methods such as analytical approximation and quadrature were developed to approximate the posterior distribution. *Monte Carlo* methods are commonly used to approximate the posterior distribution summaries $p(\theta|y)$ by taking a large number of samples. Sampling methods such as *Rejection sampling* and *Importance sampling* are used to draw independent samples, while *Markov Chain Monte Carlo* (MCMC) techniques such as *Gibbs sampling* and *Metropolis-Hasting* are used for a possibly depended sample of data points.

In the Metropolis-Hasting (MH) method, the idea is to generate new samples $\theta_i \rightarrow \theta_{i+1}$ such that the distribution of the final samples $p(\theta)$ converges to a *stationary* distribution as the

number of samples grows ($n \rightarrow \infty$) and is asymptotically equal to the underlying posterior $\rho(\theta)$. In order to generate new positions, we need a *proposal distribution* $\mathcal{Q}(\theta'_{i+1}|\theta_i)$ and a criteria to either *accept* the new sample ($\theta_{i+1} = \theta'_{i+1}$) or *reject* the proposed sample ($\theta_{i+1} = \theta_i$).

MH is a simple and general MCMC method, and a very commonly used proposal distribution is Gaussian distribution which is also referred to as *Random Walk Metropolis*. Unfortunately, the “seductive simplicity” hides a performance that typically scales poorly in large scale problems and high-dimensional phase spaces [62, 5].

More efficient MCMC techniques are based on continuous diffusion and discretised stochastic differential equations (SDEs), especially Langevin dynamics which was originally developed as a molecular dynamics model. In these techniques, the samples are drawn from a target distribution $\pi(\theta)$ with respect to a Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^d , which is usually known up to a normalisation factor:

$$\pi(\theta) \propto e^{-\beta U(\theta)}, \quad (1.3)$$

where $e^{-\beta U(\theta)}$ is *Boltzmann* distribution, $\beta = 1/\tau$ which in physical settings is a reciprocal temperature where τ denotes a temperature variable, and $U(\theta)$ denotes a potential function of parameters θ . In other words, $\pi(\theta)$ is the probability of the system being in a particular state as a function of that state’s energy and temperature. In our context of statistical modelling, we allow the temperature to be an artificial parameter which can be tuned to improve efficiency.

Langevin Monte Carlo methods, are based upon the *overdamped* Langevin dynamics that is defined by the following SDE:

$$d\theta = -\nabla U(\theta)dt + \sqrt{2\beta^{-1}}dW_t, \quad (1.4)$$

where W_t is the standard d-dimensional Wiener process [19, 41]. Overdamped Langevin paves the way for *Langevin dynamics* that is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} d\theta_t &= M^{-1}p_t dt, \\ dp_t &= -\nabla U(\theta_t)dt - \gamma M^{-1}p_t dt + \sigma dW_t, \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

where p denotes the momentum, γ is the friction, M is a positive definite mass matrix and $\sigma^2 = \frac{2\gamma}{\beta}$ is fluctuation-dissipation relation to ensure that the extended (canonical) distribution:

$$\pi_{\text{ext}} \propto \exp [\beta(p^T M^{-1}p/2)] \pi(\theta), \quad (1.6)$$

is preserved, which means if we put Eq. 1.6 into the Fokker–Planck equation associated with Eq. 1.5 the result is zero.

One challenge for sampling methods is when $U(\theta)$ is ill-conditioned. For instance, the Hessian contains large positive eigenvalues (high-curvature) and some near zero eigenvalues (low-curvature), or gradient is perpendicular to the contours. The ill-conditioning of the energy landscape is very common in high-dimensional settings. In high dimensional and non-linear systems, accessing underpinning information, for instance, frequencies of oscillations in harmonic model problem, is no longer possible, thus a few directions may restrict the progress of sampling. For example, consider a Gaussian mixture model as shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that a naive sampling path generated using a discretisation (Eq. 1.4) has been taken due to a poor choice of initial conditions.

Figure 1: Sampling path of a complex landscape using a naive canonical sampler (see [24]).

One of the attractive approaches to improve the efficiency of these sampling algorithms is to use preconditioning techniques in such a way that one does not change the invariant measure but rescale the dynamics in order to accelerate convergence.

1.2 Optimisation in high-dimensional settings

In some problems, we are interested in a point estimate from the target probability distribution, such as the mean. In the Bayesian framework this is achieved by *maximum a posteriori* (MAP), similar to *Maximum Likelihood Estimation* (MLE) in frequentist approach, which is a technique to obtain point estimates by maximising the posterior distribution over a set of parameters given specified data. Sampling and MAP estimation can be related by introducing a sampling of densities involving the negative log posterior $l(\theta) = -\ln p(\theta|y)$ such that:

$$p_\tau(\theta) = \exp(-\tau l(\theta)) = p(\theta)^{1/\tau}. \quad (1.7)$$

We can see that by setting $\tau = 1$ we obtain the posterior density, and $\tau \rightarrow 0$ gives us a sequence of distributions whose mass density is very close to the mode of the distribution. In other words, sampling can be transformed to MAP by reducing the parameter τ . The parameter τ can be thought as an artificial coefficient which is analogous to the temperature in statistical physics. MAP and MLE are optimisation problems which involve minimising an *objective function*, or *loss function* (*cost function*), to obtain a set of parameters and distribution that can describe the data most suitable.

Let us now consider a likelihood function $p(y|\theta)$. We can obtain the MLE for parameters θ by:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\text{MLE}} &= \arg \max_{\theta} p(y|\theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \prod_{i=1}^N p(y_i|\theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(y_i|\theta), \end{aligned} \quad (1.8)$$

where N is the number of data points. We use the log-likelihood to simplify the equations and improve computational efficiency. For MAP, we first need to write the posterior as a product of the likelihood and prior:

$$\begin{aligned} p(\theta|y) &= \frac{p(y|\theta)p_0(\theta)}{p(y)}, \\ &\propto p(y|\theta)p_0(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

In optimisation, we are only interested in a set of solutions which minimise the objective, so the normalisation constant is unnecessary and can be omitted. To achieve the MAP, we need to find θ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\text{MAP}} &= \arg \max_{\theta} p(y|\theta)p_0(\theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \log p(y|\theta) + \log p_0(\theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \log \prod_{i=1}^N p(y_i|\theta) + \log p_0(\theta) \\ &= \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(y_i|\theta) + \log p_0(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

In order to obtain θ_{MLE} and θ_{MAP} , we first need to derive the log-likelihood for our model, then find the set of parameters by solving an optimisation problem to maximise the likelihood. Iterative optimisation algorithms such as *gradient descent* (GD) are commonly used due to their computational efficiency, particularly in non-linear and high-dimensional models. Gradient descent finds the values of parameters that minimise a loss function by iteratively taking steps

proportional to the negative gradient of the loss function and descending towards a minimum. One main downside of gradient descent algorithm is the need to compute the gradient of the objective function over the entire dataset which can be computationally expensive in high-dimensional and large datasets. To alleviate this problem, we typically use a stochastic approximation of the gradient which uses a subset of data to perform an update. *Stochastic gradient descent* (SGD) updates the parameters of the model based on sub-sampled data which is computationally very efficient. Another advantage of SGD over GD is handling redundancy in data. For example, if we double the size of the dataset by duplicating the data, the computational cost of GD will double while SGD will be unaffected assuming the number of samples used at each step kept constant. Moreover, the stochastic effect induced by gradient noise due to sub-sampling may lead to escaping from local minima since the stationary point for the sub-sampled data is not likely to be a stationary point for the entire dataset. However, this does not guarantee convergence to a good minima and similar to sampling methods, optimisation algorithms such as SGD, may get stuck in a minimum for a long time.

In Eq. 1.7, we saw that optimisation can be thought of as a special case of sampling with zero temperature ($\tau = 0$). This relationship allows us to employ efficient sampling algorithms for optimisation. One main advantage of this approach is the exploration of the parameter space followed by convergence to an optimal minimum. One illustration that sampling-based algorithm can significantly improve convergence and performance of optimisation algorithms has been in machine learning applications [65, 24, 33]. For instance, [33] proposed a thermodynamic parameterisation algorithm for training neural networks in high-dimensional and highly non-convex classification problems, which improves the accuracy of the model and accelerates the convergence speed.

1.3 Diffusion analysis of optimisation schemes

The aim of diffusion analysis is to shed light at these questions:

- Why do some algorithms converge faster than others for the same problem with the same initial conditions?
- How can a change of hyperparameters help to speed convergence?
- Why is optimisation in some loss landscapes easier than others?

Hao Li et al. [39] proposed a technique to visualise the loss landscapes of neural networks. They observed that the models that achieve higher performance produce loss landscapes that are smoother and have less sharp minima. Figure 2 illustrates the loss landscape of the same deep neural network (DNN) architecture with a different number of hidden layers. We can see that deeper network has a rough landscape with too many minima while the shallower network produces a benign loss landscape.

If we consider parameters of our model as molecules, it would allow us to study the diffusion of parameters in the space and analyse the convergence of different models and algorithms. For instance, if we have a subset of variables which are partitioned into the different groups, we can analyse their role by looking at their diffusion coefficient. In section 5.3 we use this technique to evaluate the exploration rate of a sampling method and analyse the convergence of different neural network architectures.

(a) DNN with 50 Hidden layers

(b) DNN with 20 Hidden layers

Figure 2: Loss landscape of high-dimensional deep neural networks. The network with 50 hidden layers (a) has dramatic non-convexities and large regions, while the network with 20 hidden layers (b) has a fairly smooth landscape and a large convex contour in the middle.

1.4 A challenging molecular classification for machine learning

Molecular simulation are techniques to model the behaviour of molecules and evaluate any aspect of the properties of their structures. Molecular modelling has increasingly becoming more valuable in the investigation of biological systems and in the design of new active molecules for drug development [13]. Protein folding is an important example of molecular modelling in which the aim is to find the probability that a protein will be folded to a certain structure at a given temperature. However, there are astronomically many configurations in which the protein may fold which makes the exact enumeration of each such a “configuration” infeasible.

Bovine pancreatic trypsin inhibitor (BPTI) is a small and simple globular protein that has been studied extensively both experimentally and computationally. BPTI is an interesting protein to study because it is often used as a complex toy system for protein-protein interactions and molecular recognition and was one of the first proteins ever studied through molecular dynamics simulation [64].

DE Shaw Research generated 1 millisecond trajectory of BPTI using Anton Supercomputer [59] which contains conformational change within a folded state that involves transitions among various structures. These states are often separated by barriers on an “free energy landscape” which are referred to as “basins”. Some of these states have very rarely populated transitions as shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: Number of samples for each state.

Each datapoint consists of 174 dimensions associated with 58 Ca-atoms. The 2-d energy landscape of the equilibrium state is generated using time-lagged independent component analysis (TIC) and is shown in Figure 4 in which blue circles denote discrete states of the protein. Figure 4c illustrates a front, side and top view of the BPTI protein structure at a given state, in which each color denotes a different state. As we can see, the red state has a more flexible characteristic compared to other two states which are more compact and quite similar. The meta-stable states corresponding to the structures in 4c are shown in 4b which shows that the red state is our single event state on the right hand side.

This task is challenging for machine learning algorithms for two reasons: first, the data is very sparse which makes the training of neural network challenging, second, some states have very similar structure which makes them difficult to classify. In this thesis, we employ deep neural networks for classifying the states of the BPTI protein for a given configuration using our proposed method (PAL).

(a) Clustering of protein states for the first TIC components

(b) meta-stable states for specific structure shown in **c** for the first TIC components

(c) Protein state trajectories

Figure 4: Plot to illustrate the energy landscape for various states using time-lagged independent component analysis (TIC) (**a**). **b** shows meta-stable energy level for the particular protein state such that blue, green and red dots represent corresponding meta-stable energy for the blue, green and red structures shown in **c** respectively.

To summarise, the contribution of this thesis include:

1. A preconditioned Langevin dynamic algorithm for sampling and optimisation in ill-conditioned landscapes.
2. Motivating thermodynamics-based approaches for optimisation in high-dimensional and discussing the relation between gradient-based methods and thermodynamic methods.
3. A diffusion-based technique to study the convergence and training mechanism of deep neural network by estimating diffusion coefficient for parameters.
4. Proposing a preconditioned adaptive Langevin dynamics optimisation algorithm for high-dimensional loss landscapes
5. Demonstration of application of thermodynamics-based approaches in challenging task of protein structure classification.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

Section 2 gives a brief overview and analysis of gradient-based and thermodynamics-based optimisation methods in high-dimensional landscapes. This section begins by overiewing widely used optimisation methods for training deep neural networks, and it is followed by discussing and motivating the thermodynamics-based optimisation approaches, and finally introducing a hybrid method that combines thermodynamic with gradient-based methods.

Section 3 covers the preconditioning algorithms for efficient sampling and optimisation problems. We present a novel preconditioning technique using a mass tensor matrix (MassBAO) that accelerates convergence of sampling a target distribution by rescaling the sampling landscape. Following that, we propose an adaptive preconditioned Langevin dynamics (PAL) for large scale and high-dimensional optimisation, in particular, deep neural network training.

Section 4 presents a diffusion-based technique for analysing the optimisation mechanism in high-dimensional settings. It discusses how diffusion coefficient could help to understand the underlying mechanism in training deep neural networks.

Section 5 presents various numerical numerical experiments. First, we evaluate the performance of our preconditioned Langevin method (MassBAO) on sampling with an ill-conditioned landscape. Then, we describe the relation between temperature, diffusion coefficient and exploration of a target distributions. Additionally, we show how diffusion analysis can be used to analyse the convergence rate in deep neural network training. Further, we compare the generalisation and convergence rate of our preconditioned adaptive Langevin method (PAL) in synthesis dataset and real-world challenging protein structure classification problem.

2 Optimisation methods in high-dimensional landscapes

The most significant challenges in optimisation arise in high-dimensional problems with unknown landscape properties. Optimisation plays an important role in machine learning problems where often the problem is highly nonconvex and high-dimensional. A lot of work on developing and improving efficient optimisation strategies has been proposed. Optimisation techniques can be divided into three main categories: *first-order* such as SGD, *high-order* such as Newton’s method and *derivative-free* methods such as coordinate descent. The computational efficiency of gradient-based methods has made them the most effective approaches in high-dimensional, non-convex and large-scale problems in machine learning.

In this section, we first explore widely used optimisation algorithms for complex models, then we discuss the potential of thermodynamics approaches to improve optimisation, and finally, we introduce a hybrid strategy to combine thermodynamics and techniques from continuous optimisation.

2.1 Gradient-based optimisation methods

The *gradient descent* algorithm is a widely used starting point for deriving methods to minimise an objective function $J(\theta)$ parameterised by model parameters $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Such methods iteratively update the parameters in the opposite direction of the gradient of the objective function $\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)$ with respect to the parameters. At each iteration, the learning rate $\eta > 0$ corresponds to the size of the step which the parameters take in the descent direction. The algorithm updates all the parameters simultaneously and is given by

$$\theta_i := \theta_i - \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_i} J(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_d). \quad (2.1)$$

We will discuss three variants of gradient descent: *batch gradient descent*, *stochastic gradient descent* and *mini-batch gradient descent*; these differ in how much data is used to approximate the gradient of objective function. Let $J(\theta; X)$ represent an objective function that we wish to minimise, where θ is the vector of the parameters of the model and X represents the data. For instance, if the optimisation objective is to maximise the log-likelihood, we define the objective function as follows:

$$J(\theta; X) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(x_i | \theta), \quad (2.2)$$

where N is the number of datapoints and x_i denotes the i^{th} datapoint.

Batch Gradient Descent. *Batch gradient descent* computes the gradient of the objective function with respect to parameters θ using the entire training data:

$$\theta = \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta; X), \quad (2.3)$$

where X denotes the entire dataset. This method converges to global minimum in convex surfaces and to local minima in non-convex landscapes given an appropriate learning rate (Figure 5c) [22, 12]. One limitation of this method is memory cost as we need to feed all the training data into the optimisation algorithm to perform a single update which can also slow down the training process. Batch gradient descent cannot be used in an online setting where new samples are added on-the-fly. Moreover, training data may contain samples that are very similar and recomputing the gradient for each before updating the parameters makes batch gradient method wasteful.

Stochastic gradient descent. In contrast to batch gradient, *stochastic gradient descent* (SGD) updates the parameters as follows:

$$\theta = \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta; x^{(i)}), \quad (2.4)$$

where $x^{(i)}$ is a sample randomly drawn from the dataset without replacement. As SGD performs a parameter update for each example, it is more computationally efficient than the batch gradient method and in practice converges faster. The parameter update for each example induces a high variance and causes the value of the objective function to fluctuate during training (Figure 5a).

Figure 5: Gradient noise cause by sub-sampling of dataset at every iteration of optimisation

The fluctuation due to gradient noise enables the parameters to jump into a potentially better minimum. Although, the fluctuation may cause SGD to not converge to a unique point, it is shown that in practice, the method will converge by gradually decreasing the learning rate η (similar to the batch gradient approach). SGD almost surely converges to a local minimum in a non-convex surface and to the global minimum in the convex setting.

Mini-batch gradient descent. *Mini-batch gradient descent* is an approach which combines the benefit of gradient noise in SGD with the stability and convergence of the batch gradient method (5b). In this scheme, a “mini-batch” refers to a collection of samples of the training data with are randomly picked without replacement. Mini-batches are fed to the neural network sequentially and the gradient of the objective is computed with respect to the mini-batch. This can reduce the variance that SGD introduces which can lead to a more stable convergence. The update rule for mini-batch of size n is given by

$$\theta = \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta; x^{(i:i+n)}), \quad (2.5)$$

where $x^{(i:i+n)}$ denotes samples with a batch size of n . Similar to SGD, mini-batch gradient descent does not guarantee convergence and it introduces a few challenges such as:

- Gradient descent methods work well when an appropriate learning rate is chosen. If the learning rate is large, these methods may not converge due to the fluctuation around the minimum. On the other hand, choosing a small learning rate slows down the convergence, hence leading to a longer training process.
- The learning rate can be “scheduled” to be adjusted by an annealing process during training as in [54]. In other words, the learning rate scheduler reduces the stepsize, as training is getting closer to convergence by heuristics such as annealing based on the value of the objective function. However, this scheduler and threshold need to be pre-defined before the training process which is difficult and the method is unable to adapt to a domain characteristics [14].
- When the data is sparse, some “features” may appear with less frequency than others, therefore, it is advantageous to update parameters with different learning rates such that rare features have larger updates than frequent features. *Features* refer to properties and characteristics of input data. For instance, in image recognition tasks, a feature can refer to an object that is present in the image, or a characteristic of objects.
- In highly nonconvex surfaces, SGD is likely to get trapped in a sub-optimal local minimum due to the proliferation of local minima in the non-convex surface. However, it has been shown that in a deep neural network it is saddle points that cause difficulty in training rather than local minima [15]. The saddle points are usually surrounded by high error plateaus that can dramatically slow down the training process and may give the illusory impression of being trapped in a sub-optimal minimum.

To address the aforementioned challenges, various modifications of SGD have been developed. The following are the most efficient and widely used SGD-based optimisation algorithms for high-dimensional settings such as deep neural networks.

Stochastic gradient descent with momentum (SGD-M).

One of the main problems with steepest descent is that it is a particularly poor procedure when surfaces have ravines where the gradient is large in some directions and small in others [61]. The objective functions of neural networks have surfaces with many ravines and vanilla steepest descent may perform poorly. In this situation, SGD oscillates across the slope of the ravine leading to hesitant progress towards the local optimum as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: (a) shows the oscillation of SGD in ravines, and (b) illustrates the effect of momentum is dampening the oscillation. The convergence of two methods is computed by mean square error (MSE) and is shown in (c).

In a Newtonian particle model, the *momentum* corresponds to the product of mass and velocity. In training a statistical model, “momentum” is introduced by use of an artificial parameter which mimics the role in physical momentum. If we consider the behaviour of SGD near a local minima as a set of couples and harmonic oscillators, the artificial momentum can help to accelerate across the flat region in the landscape and can potentially improve exploration of multimodal systems by crossing barriers (Figure 6b). SGD-M updates the parameters by adding a fraction term γ which effectively averages out the gradient of the past timesteps.

$$\begin{aligned} v_{t+1} &= \gamma v_t - \eta \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_t), \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t + v_{t+1}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

where v is the velocity vector. Essentially, momentum helps the gradient to descend faster in the regions where the gradient points in the same direction as the velocity direction and slows down the updates in regions where gradient changes direction. SGD-M method can be improved by adding *Nesterov's accelerated gradient* (NAG) [49] which estimates the momentum term based on the approximation of the next update. NAG has a better convergence rate guarantee in smooth convex surfaces and deterministic gradient. It does this by estimating the gradient of the objective with respect to $\theta - \gamma v_t$. The update rule for NAG is given by

$$\begin{aligned} v_{t+1} &= \gamma v_t - \eta \nabla J(\theta_t + \gamma v_t), \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta + v_{t+1}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

Figure 7 shows a single parameter update using SGD-M and NAG. SGD-M estimates the gradient with respect to the current parameters first and then updates them in the direction of the updated accumulated gradient, while, NAG anticipates the future value for parameters and then estimates the gradient and makes a correction.

Figure 7: (a) SGD-M, (b) NAG

The following algorithms are variants of SGD and SGD-M which adapt learning rate to accelerate convergence.

Adaptive gradient algorithm (AdaGrad)

Choosing an appropriate learning rate greatly influences the performance of the optimisation procedure. This can be challenging, particularly in high-dimensional loss landscapes where we have no information about the geometry of the surface. This becomes more crucial in the context of deep neural networks when the data features are sparse. The sparsity of features can lead to poor parameterisation as some parameters are updated infrequently compared to other parameters associated with frequent features. However, these infrequent features could be highly informative and discriminative.

Adaptive methods adjust the learning rate automatically during the training process. *Adaptive gradient algorithm* (AdaGrad) is a family of SGD methods that performs efficient parameter update by estimating the gradient in such a way as to dynamically incorporate knowledge of the geometry of the data observed in earlier iterations. In other words, it adapts the learning rate such that larger updates occur for infrequent features and smaller updates for frequent features. This characteristic of AdaGrad makes it suitable for dealing with sparse data.

For brevity, we define $g_{t,i}$ to be the partial derivative of the objective function with respect to parameters θ_i at timestep t :

$$g_{t,i} = \frac{\partial J(\theta_{t,i})}{\partial \theta_{t,i}}. \tag{2.8}$$

We can rewrite the SGD update for every parameter θ_i at each timestep t :

$$\theta_{t+1,i} = \theta_{t,i} - \eta g_{t,i}. \quad (2.9)$$

AdaGrad adjusts the learning rate for parameters by using the historical gradient from the previous iterations. The update rule that AdaGrad employs is as follows:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta G_t^{-1/2} g_t, \quad (2.10)$$

where the matrix $G_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ defined as $G_t = \sum_{t=0}^T g_t g_t^T$ is the sum of the outer product of previous gradients. In subsection 3.3 we show that $g_t g_t^T$ is an approximation of Hessian matrix using thermodynamics approaches. The computation of the square root of the matrix G_t can be expensive. In order to improve the efficiency of the algorithm, a diagonal approximation of G_t is used. Lets us denote the diagonal matrix

$$\Gamma_t = \begin{bmatrix} G_{t,11} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & G_{t,22} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & G_{t,dd} \end{bmatrix}$$

to represent the diagonal approximation of the matrix G_t . Then, we can rewrite the Eq. 2.10 using the diagonal approximation Γ_t such that

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta \Gamma_t^{-1/2} g_t, \quad (2.11)$$

where $\Gamma_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a diagonal matrix where the diagonal entries are the sums of the squares of the gradient with respect to θ_i up to time step t . To avoid division by zero, the smoothing term ϵI , with I being the Identity matrix and ϵ a small positive scalar, is added to the diagonal matrix Γ_t . The final update rule of AdaGrad is expressed as:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta (\Gamma_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I) g_t. \quad (2.12)$$

The reason for the square root operation is not theoretically justified, however, it turns out to be a crucial operation since the optimisation process becomes unstable without it.

The main advantage of AdaGrad is that it automatically adapts the learning rate for each parameter, hence it eliminates tuning of the learning rate parameter. However, as the learning rate is divided by the term that contains G_t which is the accumulated sum of gradients, it shrinks and eventually becomes infinitesimally small. at which point the learning process is no longer effective. On the other hand, since the magnitudes of gradients are factored out, AdaGrad can be very sensitive to the initial conditions, where an initial large gradients can lead to small learning rate for the remaining training process.

Adaptive learning rate method (AdaDelta)

Adaptive learning rate method (AdaDelta) was proposed in [68] to overcome the challenges in AdaGrad algorithm such as sensitivity to initial conditions and continual learning rate decay.

To eliminate the problem of learning rate decay, AdaDelta restricts accumulating the past gradient to a fixed window size w , in contrast to AdaGrad where the cumulative sum of the all past squared gradients is computed. The windowed accumulation of squared gradients becomes a local estimate using the recent gradient which avoids the potentially singular denominator in AdaGrad (Eq. 2.12), hence the learning continues to make progress even after many parameter updates. However, storing w previous squared gradients can be inefficient, therefore, an exponentially decaying average is used to compute the rescaling matrix for each update. The exponential decaying average with a decay parameter ρ can be stored in a diagonal matrix recursively in the

form

$$D_t = \begin{cases} \Psi_1 & t = 1 \\ \rho\Psi_t + (1 - \rho)D_{t-1} & t > 1 \end{cases},$$

where $D_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a diagonal matrix of exponentially decayed squared gradients, $\Psi_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is diagonal matrix of squared of gradient at timestep t defined as

$$\Psi_t = \begin{bmatrix} g_{t,1}^2 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & g_{t,2}^2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & g_{t,d}^2 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $g_{t,i}$ represent the gradient with respect to θ_i at timestep t .

Similar to AdaGrad method, the resulting update rule is:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta(D_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I)g_t, \quad (2.13)$$

or

$$\Delta\theta_t = -\eta(D_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I)g_t. \quad (2.14)$$

By looking at $\Delta\theta_t$, we see that the units are not compatible. In other words, the parameters do not have the same hypothetical units as the parameter update $\Delta\theta$. Indeed, when considering SGD, SGD-M and AdaGrad, the parameter update doesn't have the same units as the parameters. In scalar case, we can do a simple unit analysis to understand the relation in parameter update. For instance, the units in SGD-M relate to the gradient instead of parameter

$$\text{units of } \Delta\theta \propto \text{units of } g \propto \frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta} \propto \frac{1}{\text{units of } \theta}, \quad (2.15)$$

where f is the cost function and assumed to be unitless and g denotes the vector of gradients. In contrast, second-order methods such as Newton's method that use second derivative information provide parameters updates which have the same units as the parameters

$$\Delta\theta \propto \mathcal{H}^{-1}g \propto \frac{\partial f}{\partial^2 f} \propto \text{units of } \theta. \quad (2.16)$$

With the assumption that the Hessian is diagonal, we can rearrange Newton's method so that

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{\frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta}}{\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \theta^2}} \Rightarrow \frac{1}{\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \theta^2}} = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta}}. \quad (2.17)$$

Since in Eq. 2.14, the term $(D_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I)$ already represents the $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta}$ in the denominator of Eq. 2.17, we only need to define a measure of the $\Delta\theta$ quantity in the numerator. However, $\Delta\theta_t$ for the current update is unknown, so we can locally approximate it by computing the exponential decaying average of the previous $\Delta\theta$, by assuming that the curvature is locally smooth. So the AdaDelta algorithm can update parameters with the same unit by defining the parameter update such that

$$\Delta\theta_t = -(C_{t-1}^{1/2} + \epsilon I)(D_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I)g_t, \quad (2.18)$$

where the diagonal matrix $C_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is the exponential decaying average of $\Delta\theta$. The diagonal entries are computed recursively as

$$C_{t,ii} = \rho C_{t-1,ii} + (1 - \rho) \Delta\theta_{t,i}, \quad (2.19)$$

for $i \in 1, \dots, d$.

As result, we can see in Eq. 2.18 that the update rule doesn't need a learning rate η . This

is very beneficial in applications where choosing an appropriate learning rate is difficult.

Adaptive moment estimation (Adam)

Adaptive moment estimation (Adam) [29] can be thought as the combination of SGD-M and AdaDelta. Adam stores an exponentially decaying average of past squared gradients similar to AdaDelta as well as an exponentially decaying average of past gradients similar to SGD-M.

Let g_1, g_2, \dots represent the gradients of the stochastic objective f as successive timesteps. Similar to SGD-M (Eq. 2.6), we define the exponentially weighted average gradient by

$$v_t = \beta_1 v_{t-1} - (1 - \beta_1) \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_t), \quad (2.20)$$

where v_t is the exponentially decayed gradient up to the timestep t and β_1 denotes the decay factor.

The second-moment estimate is computed by exponentially decaying the square of gradient as in the AdaDelta algorithm (Eq. 2.18). we can initialise the exponential moving average as $D_0 = 0$ (a diagonal matrix of zeros in $\mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$). Then, the update at time step t of the exponential moving average of second-moment is

$$D_t = \begin{cases} \Psi_1 & t = 1 \\ \rho \Psi_t + (1 - \rho) D_{t-1} & t > 1 \end{cases},$$

where $\Psi_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a diagonal matrix with the squared partials as diagonal entries as defined for AdaDelta method.

The exponential moving average can be also written as a function of the gradients of previous timesteps such that

$$D_t = (1 - \beta_2) \sum_{i=1}^t \beta_2^{t-i} \Psi_i. \quad (2.21)$$

Let us denote the mean of diagonal entries of D_t by $\text{Avg}[D_t]$. To correct the discrepancy between $\text{Avg}[D_t]$ and true second moment gradients $\text{E}[\Psi_t]$, we take the expectation of the left and right hand sides of Eq. 2.21

$$\begin{aligned} \text{E}[D_t] &= \text{E} \left[(1 - \beta_2) \sum_{i=1}^t \beta_2^{t-i} \Psi_i \right] \\ &= \text{E}[\Psi] \cdot (1 - \beta_2) \sum_{i=1}^t \beta_2^{t-i} + \xi \\ &= \text{E}[\Psi] \cdot (1 - \beta_2^t) + \xi, \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

where $\xi = 0$ if the true second moment is stationary and very small otherwise. The remaining term $(1 - \beta_2^t)$ that is caused by the initialisation of $D_0 = 0$ induces a bias which can be corrected by dividing both sides of the equation by $(1 - \beta_2^t)$. The derivation of the first moment is completely analogous. Therefore, the first and second-moment estimates can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} v_t &= \beta_1 v_{t-1} - (1 - \beta_1) \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_t), \\ D_t &= \beta_2 D_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \Psi_t, \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

and the bias-corrected estimates are

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{v}_t &= \frac{1}{1 - \beta_1^t} v_t, \\ \hat{D}_t &= \frac{1}{1 - \beta_2^t} D_t, \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in [0, 1)$ are hyperparameters controlling the exponential decay rates of these moving averages. Using the corrected-bias estimate, the update rule is

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta (\hat{D}_t + \epsilon \mathbf{I})^{-1/2} \hat{v}_t, \quad (2.25)$$

where ϵ is a small value which is added to avoid division zero. We can see if we set $\beta_1 = 0$ we obtain AdaDelta (Eq. 2.18), and by setting $\beta_2 = 0$ we derive SGD-M methods (Eq. 2.6).

Despite the success of adaptive algorithms such as AdaGrad, AdaDelta and Adam, A.C. Wilson et al [66] showed that adaptive methods often find drastically different solutions than gradient descent (GD) or stochastic gradient descent (SGD). They found that Adaptive methods could get stuck in local minima while SGD and GD achieve zero test error. Additionally, they observed that adaptive methods found worse solutions than SGD in state-of-the-art deep learning models which suggests that adaptive methods can overfit to the data, hence having less generalisation capability compared to GD and SGD.

On the other hand, it is not clear why adaptive methods outperform non-adaptive methods in some problems and vice-versa. For instance, Adam is hard to beat for training Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [53, 26] and Q-learning with function approximation [40, 44], although both of these applications stand out because they are not actually solving optimization problems.

We speculate that current adaptive methods for deep neural networks are based on assumptions and heuristics that don't hold in general. For instance, Wilson et al [66] proved that AdaGrad fails to generalise by constructing a particularly pernicious generative model. Other adaptive algorithms such as AdaDelta and Adam are built upon the assumptions in AdaGrad. We argue that these adaptive methods can also fail where the AdaGrad assumptions don't hold.

In the next subsection we describe the potential for thermodynamics-based approaches to improve optimisation of high-dimensional landscapes.

2.2 Thermodynamics-based approaches

To motivate sampling-based optimisation algorithms in high dimensional settings, we first, introduce an analogy between statistical physics and machine learning and look at gradient-based methods from a thermodynamic perspective.

We can think of each parameter θ_i in a model as a particle i with a velocity p_i and a position $q_i = \theta_i$ in a physical system. According to classical thermodynamics and statistical mechanics, particles settle into the neighbourhood of an energetic minimum. The knob that adjusts the balance between energetic and entropic forces is *temperature*. Similarly, we can think of neural network training as a process in which the parameters θ settle into a configuration that minimises an objective function. Therefore, we can define a link between thermodynamics and machine learning such that

$$\text{potential energy } U(q) \equiv \text{objective function}(\theta).$$

Statistical mechanics is traditionally concerned with equilibrium states in which the energy is minimum for the given entropy. In non-equilibrium statistical mechanics, the process taking places between the initial conditions and equilibrium state is called *relaxation* which is analogous to the transformation from initial values of parameters θ to parameters in which the minimum objective is achieved.

relaxation from an initial non-equilibrium state \equiv optimising parameters of model

A fundamental difference between molecules in an equilibrium state and neural network parameters after training is that the individual molecules are constantly moving around while the neural network parameters are fixed. In other words, molecules positions are characterised by a probability distribution while the neural network parameters are viewed as a point estimate. To fill this gap between the thermodynamic system and neural network, we need to introduce a probability distribution over the parameters. This will give us several advantages such as

- The ability to quantify uncertainty in a prediction,
- The means to reduce the variability in outcomes of learning algorithms,
- The avoidance of over-fitting to the training samples due to an induced regularisation by thermodynamics.

The probability distribution associated to a given energy function in statistical mechanics is defined by a *Boltzmann* distribution

$$p_i \propto e^{-\beta E(\theta_i)}, \quad (2.26)$$

where $\beta = 1/T$ and T is the temperature, and $E(\theta_i)$ denotes the energy of that state.

By considering the objective function as an energy function, The Boltzmann distribution for neural network parameters can be written as

$$p(\theta) \propto e^{-\beta J(\theta)}. \quad (2.27)$$

If we specify our objective function as the mean squared error

$$J(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^N (f(x_i; \theta) - y_i)^2, \quad (2.28)$$

in which N is the number of training samples, x_i and y_i represent a training samples and its label respectively. Therefore, we can rewrite the probability density over parameters in the form

$$p(\theta) \propto \exp \left[-\beta \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N (f(x_i; \theta) - y_i)^2 \right]. \quad (2.29)$$

Computing the objective function for a single data point is easy, however, computing the above probability density is not trivial. If we consider the output of a neural network for an input x_i under the probability density, we obtain the expected value

$$\hat{y} = \int p(\theta) f(x_i; \theta) d\theta, \quad (2.30)$$

where the integral is intractable in deep neural networks where the number of parameters may exceed hundreds of millions.

This integral cannot be estimated using traditional grid-based Monte Carlo methods for two reasons: first, we know what $p(\theta)$ is proportional to (Eq. 2.29), and the normalising constant is another hard integral; second, the probability density in a high-dimensional space tends to be very concentrated. An alternative method to estimate the integral is using MCMC algorithm such as Metropolis-Hastings (MH). Random walk Metropolis produces successive samples which are highly correlated which reduces the sampling efficiency.

A more efficient type of MH method is Hamiltonian Monte Carlo [48] in which each parameter θ has a position and another parameter which represents its momenta p . HMC reduces the correlation between samples to maintain a high probability of acceptance. We can define a total energy function, or Hamiltonian, as the sum of the MSE and kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}|p|^2$ and write the joint probability density for θ and p as

$$p(\theta, p) \propto \exp \left[\beta \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N (f(x_i; \theta) - y_i)^2 + \frac{1}{2}|p|^2 \right]. \quad (2.31)$$

We can sample from this distribution. Having the momentum terms allows us to choose the next update using Hamiltonian dynamics. The main limitation of this method emerges when the number of parameters and training examples increases which makes it inefficient for modern datasets and architectures that have millions of parameters and millions of examples.

In the next section, we discuss more computationally efficient algorithms which are based on thermodynamic parameterisation.

Stochastic gradient Langevin dynamics (SGLD)

Monte Carlo methods require to go through the entire dataset at each iteration which is computationally expensive. Welling and Teh proposed an alternative method based on Langevin dynamics to make neural networks probabilistic while remaining tractable for big datasets [65]. Their proposed method uses a Robbins-Monro type algorithm which stochastically optimises a likelihood, while noise is added into the parameter updates through Langevin dynamics in order to converge to the full posterior distribution.

We can define a parameter update for stochastic optimisation [55] at each iteration for a subset of n data items $X_t = \{x_{t1}, \dots, x_{tn}\}$ as follows:

$$\Delta\theta_t = \frac{\epsilon_t}{2} \left(\nabla \log p(\theta_t) + \frac{N}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla \log p(x_{ti}|\theta_t) \right), \quad (2.32)$$

where $p(\theta)$ is a prior density $p(x|\theta)$ is the probability of data item x given our model parameterised by θ , N is the number of datapoints and ϵ_t is sequence of stepsizes. To ensure convergence, the sequence of stepsizes must satisfy

$$\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \epsilon_t = \infty, \quad \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \epsilon_t^2 < \infty. \quad (2.33)$$

Typically, stepsizes $\epsilon_t = a(b+t)^{-\gamma}$ decay with $\gamma \in (0.5, 1]$.

To capture uncertainty and prevent overfitting, a Langevin dynamics framework can be used instead of MCMC techniques as a more efficient type of sampling method. These are motivated

as the discretisation of a stochastic differential equation whose equilibrium distribution is the posterior distribution. Langevin dynamics takes gradient steps but also injects Gaussian noise into the parameter update such that

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\theta_t &= \frac{\epsilon}{2} \left(\nabla\log p(\theta_t) + \frac{N}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla\log p(x_i|\theta_t) \right) + \eta_t, \\ \eta_t &\sim N(0, \epsilon).\end{aligned}\tag{2.34}$$

One way to correct for the discretisation error is to use Eq. 2.34 as a proposal distribution and correct using Metropolis-Hastings procedure. We can see the discretisation error decreases by decreasing the value of ϵ as well as increasing the acceptance rate in Metropolis-Hastings.

Looking at the similarities between stochastic gradient algorithms 2.32 and Langevin dynamics 2.34, we can combine the two to allow efficient use of large datasets while allowing for parameter uncertainty to be captured in a Bayesian manner. Therefore, the update for Stochastic Gradient Langevin Dynamics can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\theta_t &= \frac{\epsilon_t}{2} \left(\nabla\log p(\theta_t) + \frac{N}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla\log p(x_{ti}|\theta_t) \right) + \eta_t, \\ \eta_t &\sim N(0, \epsilon_t),\end{aligned}\tag{2.35}$$

where stepsizes converge to zero slowly enough to allow averaging out over the stochasticity in the gradients. Moreover, by decreasing the stepsize to zero, Metropolis-Hastings (MH) rejection rate goes to zero asymptotically, so the MH acceptance step which requires evaluation of probabilities over the whole dataset can be omitted [65]. SGLD can be thought as the combination of Metropolis-adjusted Langevin algorithm (MALA) with stochastic gradient estimation and elimination of the acceptance step.

While decreasing stepsizes results in weak convergence to the posterior distribution, SGLD is often used with constant stepsize. By setting the stepsize to be inversely proportional to N where N is the number of the training samples, SGLD algorithm has an invariant probability measure which significantly departs from the target posterior and behaves like SGD [8]. It is argued that the high variance of stochastic gradients can limit the usefulness of SGLD in practice.

Underdamped Langevin dynamics

We can model gradient descent optimisation schemes using a system of ODEs of the form

$$d\theta = G(\theta)dt,\tag{2.36}$$

where the function $G = -\nabla J(\theta)$ and $\nabla J(\theta)$ is the gradient of loss function with respect to the parameters θ . We can use the explicit Euler method to obtain

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + hG(\theta_t),\tag{2.37}$$

where $h > 0$ denotes the stepsize. As we discussed in section 2, we use mini-batches of data for training which induces gradient noise in the dynamics. This noise can be approximately modelled by replacing G by $\tilde{G} = G(\theta) + \Sigma(\theta)R$ where $\Sigma\Sigma^T$ is the noise covariance matrix and R a standard normal random vector with i.i.d components. Thus can rewrite Eq. 2.37 in a new form

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + hG(\theta_t) + h\Sigma(\theta_t)R_t,\tag{2.38}$$

which is equivalent to the Euler-Maruyama discretisation of the Ito SDE [51]:

$$d\theta = G(\theta)dt + \sqrt{h}\Sigma(\theta)dW,\tag{2.39}$$

which is driven by multiplicative noise. The gradient noise defined by $\Sigma(\theta)$ is complicated which makes the SDE have an unknown invariant distribution which depends on the sub-sampling procedure.

In [35] a thermodynamics-based sampling method was proposed which uses additive noise to stabilise the invariant measure of stochastic dynamics similar to SGLD algorithm. However, the underdamped Langevin dynamics framework was used by applying state-of-the-art discretization methods [25, 37], which introduces additive noise within second-order stochastic dynamics.

The SDE (2.39) can be modified with the addition of momenta, resulting in an *underdamped Langevin dynamics* [31] where the friction matrix Γ that is allowed to vary with position q (which correspondence to parameters θ)

$$\begin{aligned} dq &= p dt, \\ dp &= G(q) dt - \Gamma(q) p dt + \Sigma(q) dW. \end{aligned} \tag{2.40}$$

In the special case where $\Sigma\Sigma^T = 2\tau\Gamma$, the dynamics obeys a fluctuation-dissipation theorem, and under some mild assumption is provably ergodic. This ensures that the long term solution of the dynamic sample the density $\rho_\tau(\theta, p)$ where

$$(\theta, p) := \rho_t(\theta) \times N(p|0, \tau) \propto \exp[-(L(\theta) + \|p\|^2/2)/\tau]. \tag{2.41}$$

It is common to set $\Gamma = \gamma I$ and $\Sigma = \sqrt{2\gamma\tau}I$ as the above density does not depend on the friction term Γ . Note that gradient noise would destroy the preservation of Eq. 2.41.

Splitting Scheme Splitting methods are popular discretisation schemes for Langevin dynamics [31, 32]. These methods are developed by writing the vector field as an additive decomposition (a “splitting”) into separate parts and solving for each piece in sequence. We use a Langevin splitting into pieces denoted A , B and O :

$$d \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} p \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}_A dt + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ G(\theta) \end{bmatrix}}_B dt + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -\gamma p dt + \sqrt{2\gamma\tau} dW \end{bmatrix}}_O. \tag{2.42}$$

Individual updates maps of the splitting pieces are then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_h^A(\theta, p) &= (\theta + hp, p), \\ \mathcal{U}_h^B(\theta, p) &= (\theta, p + hG(\theta)), \\ \mathcal{U}_h^O(q, p) &= (\theta, e^{-\gamma h} + \sqrt{\tau(1 - e^{-2\gamma h})}R), \end{aligned} \tag{2.43}$$

where the last expression can be obtained by studying the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck SDE and R is a d -dimensional Gaussian random variables.

We now point out the connection between underdamped Langevin and stochastic gradient descent algorithms. This connection allows us to develop a hybrid algorithm which combines underdamped Langevin and SGD approaches. One advantage of such an approach is exploration of the loss landscape before converging to a minimum. We emphasise that this connection is via an artificial temperature parameter τ which allows the gradual switching within these algorithms.

Hybrid algorithms

We will use the term “hybrid” to refer to methods which modify their features and characteristics during simulations. For instance, the integration of initial value problem for the ordinary differential equation of the form $\frac{dy}{dx} = f(x, y)$ can be computed by combination of one-step methods (e.g. Runge-Kutta) and multistep methods (e.g. Adams’ method). Modification of stepsize during simulation is another way to hybridising a numerical method.

In an optimisation problem, we often need to modify stepsizes when the geometry of landscape change from slow variant to places where there is rapid changes. Practitioner in machine learning have developed various “scheduling” strategies to modify the learning rate during the optimisation stage. Adaptive timestepping methods adjust their stepsize automatically based on the gradient information.

Another hybridisation approach is the switching of a numerical method during the simulation. This type of hybrid algorithm is advantageous in the situation where we need to use a particular property of each method at a different stage of simulation.

In this section, we introduce a hybrid algorithm which leverages the exploration capability of thermodynamic approaches such as underdamped Langevin and eventually converges to a minimum by switching to a gradient descent algorithm such as SGD-M. We observe next that SGD-M is a special case of underdamped Langevin where the temperature τ is set to zero.

2.2.0.1 Explore first, converge later

Adaptive methods such as Adam, AdaDelta and AdaGrad have superior training outcomes, however, they have been found to generalise poorly compared to SGD. In other words, these methods tends to perform well in the initial phase of training but are outperformed by SGD at later stages of training. N.S Keshar proposed a hybrid algorithm which begins the training by adaptive methods and switches to SGD when appropriate [67, 1, 28].

Langevin dynamic optimisation methods tend to find the neighbourhood of minima faster than SGD methods [33]. However, due to the sampling nature of this algorithm, they never converge completely to the minima. We take a hybrid approach which uses Langevin dynamic methods for exploration and finding minima, and then converge to the minima by switching to the SGD algorithm.

One challenge with a switching algorithm is the choice of hyperparameters such as learning rate after switching. We show that the underdamped Langevin dynamic can be reduced to SGD-M as the temperature becomes zero ($\tau \rightarrow 0$). Consider the Langevin dynamics system

$$\begin{aligned} d\theta &= p dt, \\ dp &= G(\theta) dt - \gamma p dt + \sqrt{2\gamma\tau} dW, \end{aligned} \tag{2.44}$$

where $G(\theta) := -\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)$ is the negative gradient of the loss function with respect to θ . As $\tau \rightarrow 0$, and replacing $G(\theta)$ by $-\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)$, the above system reduces to a system of ODEs

$$\begin{aligned} d\theta &= p dt, \\ dp &= -\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) dt - \gamma p dt. \end{aligned} \tag{2.45}$$

We now use the symplectic-Euler (one-sided Euler) discretisation method [36] to solve the above ODE

$$\begin{aligned} p_{t+1} &= p_t - \eta\gamma p_t - \eta\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_t), \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t + \eta p_{t+1}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.46}$$

The above equations can be simplified by factoring p_t

$$\begin{aligned} p_{t+1} &= (1 - \gamma\eta)p_t - \eta\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta_t), \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t + \eta p_{t+1}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.47}$$

Now if we set $\eta = 1$, change the variable name p to v , scale the objective function such that $\hat{J}(\theta) = \eta J(\theta)$ and define $1 - \gamma = \mu$ we have SGD-M (Eq. 2.6) in the form

$$\begin{aligned} v_{t+1} &= \mu v_t - \eta\nabla_{\theta_t} \hat{J}(\theta_t), \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t + v_{t+1}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.48}$$

where μ is the momentum parameter and η is the learning rate. The underdamped Langevin algorithm can be transformed to SGD-M by annealing the temperature and converged to the minima. We derive SGD by setting the friction parameter $\gamma = 0$. The consequence of this correspondence is identification of a natural choice of parameter which allows to make a transition in parameters between these two methods. This is similar to but distinct derivation of SGD-M from underdamped Langevin discussed in [33].

In the next section, we explore preconditioning methods for sampling and optimisation problems. We introduce a preconditioning method to accelerate convergence by rescaling the landscape using an adaptive mass preconditioning matrix (MassBAO). We also propose a preconditioned adaptive Langevin dynamics for optimisation in high-dimensional settings (PAL).

3 Preconditioning and adaptive timestepping methods

Preconditioning techniques are often used to accelerate convergence of iterative numerical methods for ill-conditioned systems. In a linear systems such as $Ax = b$, preconditioning matrix P of the matrix A is such that $P^{-1}A$ has a low condition number. This preconditioning can be useful in accelerating iterative methods to solve a linear system $Ax = b$ by solving $P^{-1}(Ax - b) = 0$ instead. The preconditioner matrix P should be chosen such that it is computationally cheap to invert as it needs to be performed at each iteration. The optimal condition number of 1 is achieved if we set $P = A$, which requires us to solve $P^{-1} = A^{-1}$ which is just the original linear system. The computationally cheapest preconditioner is $P = I$ which has no effect on the preconditioned linear system. In first-order optimisation, preconditioning can accelerate the convergence by effectively changing the geometry of the objective landscape. We can define a general preconditioning form for the gradient-based algorithm as follows

$$x_{t+1} = x_t - \gamma_t P^{-1} \nabla F(x_t) \quad (3.1)$$

where $\gamma_t \geq 0$ is stepsize, $-\nabla F(x_t)$ is negative gradient of the function at x_t .

To illustrate how preconditioning rescales the objective and accelerates convergence, we consider an objective function of the form $F(x, y) = x^2 + 8y^2$. The gradient with respect to x and y is $2x$ and $16y$ respectively. Then, a gradient descent update for each parameter is

$$\begin{aligned} x_{t+1} &= x_t - \gamma(2x_t), \\ y_{t+1} &= y_t - \gamma(16y_t). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

If we used the Hessian matrix $\mathcal{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 16 \end{pmatrix}$ as a preconditioner matrix, the preconditioned gradient update becomes

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_{t+1} \\ y_{t+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_t \\ y_t \end{pmatrix} - \gamma \mathcal{H}^{-1} \nabla F(x_t), \quad (3.3)$$

which after substitution of inverse hessian and gradient we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x_{t+1} &= x_t - \gamma x_t, \\ y_{t+1} &= y_t - \gamma y_t. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 8b illustrates how preconditioning rescales the dynamics from ellipse to circle such that preconditioned gradient descent takes straight steps while plain gradient descent follows the ellipse geometry.

Figure 8: Plain gradient descent (a) shows how gradient update fluctuates due to the elliptic geometry, while the preconditioned gradient update shows a straight line to the minimum (b) (star sign denotes the starting point).

In this section, we first discuss some popular preconditioning methods in sampling distribution and optimisation. Then, we introduce a preconditioning technique which is inspired by mass preconditioning in molecular dynamic simulations. Finally, we propose an adaptive underdamped Langevin method which is computationally efficient for large scale problems.

3.1 Quasi-Newton methods

The success of higher-order methods such as Newton’s method lies in the fact that they incorporate curvature information at each iteration. Despite the convergence guarantee for convex problems, these methods are often computationally expensive and are not often used for very large scale problems. In sampling methods such as MCMC, preconditioning techniques aim to reduce the computational cost while increasing the acceptance rate. Similarly, in optimisation problems, preconditioning helps to accelerate convergence by using curvature information.

Ensemble samplers with affine invariance. *Ensemble samplers with affine invariance* is a computationally efficient preconditioned MCMC method which uses curvature information collected by simultaneous multiple samplers[23]. For K walkers, we define an ensemble of those walkers by $S = X_k$ where the proposal distribution for each walker K depends on the current position of remaining walkers. To update the position of a walker X_k , a randomly chosen walker from the complementary ensemble $S_{[k]} = X_j, \forall j \neq k$ is drawn and an updated position is proposed by

$$X_k(t) \rightarrow X_j + Z[X_k - X_j], \quad (3.5)$$

where Z is a random variable with the density $g(Z = z)$. The authors of [23] proposed a particular form for $g(z)$ as follows:

$$g(z) \propto \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{z}} & z \in [\frac{1}{a}, a] \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where a is an adjustable scaling factor which is commonly set to 2. This method significantly improves the convergence rate of MCMC methods compared to Metropolis-Hastings (MH) methods with no additional computational overhead.

Stochastic quasi-Newton (SQN). *Stochastic quasi-Newton* (SQN) methods are a family of stochastic higher order methods which have been proposed to handle large scale non-linear optimisation [56, 10, 47]. If we denote B as the approximate matrix of Hessian matrix, and set $s_t = \theta_{t+1} - \theta_t$ and $u_t = \nabla f(\theta_{t+1}) - \nabla f(\theta_t)$ to be changes in parameters and gradients respectively, the matrix B_{t+1} satisfies

$$u_t = B_{t+1}s_t, \quad (3.6)$$

which is referred to as quasi-Newton condition, or secant equation. The search direction rule is

$$d_t = -B_t^{-1}g_t, \quad (3.7)$$

where g_t is the gradient. Having the update direction, we can obtain quasi-Newton update rule as

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + \eta_t d_t, \quad (3.8)$$

where η_t denotes the stepsize. Various effective update rules for the matrix B have been proposed, of which the important ones are **DFP** by the physicist William C, Davidon [16], and **BFGS** [58, 9, 20, 21] which is the base algorithm for SQN. In BFGS, the matrix B_{t+1} is obtained by

$$B_{t+1}^{\text{BFGS}} = B_t - \frac{B_t s_t s_t^T B_t}{s_t^T B_t s_t} + \frac{u_t u_t^T}{u_t^T u_t}. \quad (3.9)$$

In this class of algorithm, $H_t = B_t^{-1}$ to represent the inverse of B . The corresponding H for B_{t+1}^{BFGS} is given by

$$H_{t+1}^{\text{BFGS}} = (I - \frac{s_t u_t^T}{s_t^T u_t}) H_t (I - \frac{u_t s_t^T}{s_t^T u_t}) + \frac{u_t s_t^T}{s_t^T u_t}. \quad (3.10)$$

In the stochastic setting, where a sub-sample of data is fed to the model, since

$$\nabla F(\theta_{t+1}) - \nabla F(\theta_t) \approx \nabla^2 F(\theta_t)(\theta_{t+1} - \theta_t), \quad (3.11)$$

we can rewrite u_t as

$$u_t := \nabla^2 F_{S_t^H}(\theta_t) s_t \quad (3.12)$$

which is the main idea in SQN framework. Recently, SQN has gained popularity and more work has been done upon SQN to improve the algorithm [45, 46].

Figure 9: Slow convergence of BHHH algorithm and instability near the minimum (star sign denotes the starting point).

3.2 Berndt–Hall–Hall–Hausman (BHHH)

In optimisation problems which are usually concerned with maximum likelihood, a good candidate for preconditioner matrix is an approximation based on the information matrix equality. *Berndt–Hall–Hall–Hausman* (BHHH) [4] is a numerical optimisation method which replaces Hessian in Newton’s method with the outer product of the gradient which is based on the information matrix equality which states the negative expected value of Hessian can be computed by the outer product of the gradient, i.e.

$$-\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{H}(\theta)] = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\frac{\partial F(\theta)}{\partial \theta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F(\theta)}{\partial \theta} \right)^T \right]. \quad (3.13)$$

Supposed we have a log likelihood function $F(\theta)$ in the form

$$F(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^N f(y_t, \theta), \quad (3.14)$$

where y_t denotes the data. BHHH updates parameters as follow:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \eta_t A_t \nabla F(\theta_t), \quad (3.15)$$

where

$$A_t = \left[\left(\frac{\partial F(\theta_t)}{\partial \theta_t} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F(\theta_t)}{\partial \theta_t} \right)^T \right]^{-1}. \quad (3.16)$$

This method still finds the correct maximum even if the function $F(\theta)$ is not log-likelihood BHHH is essentially a hill-climbing algorithm and the good choice of A only affects the speed of the hill-climbing process, however, it is likely to slow down the convergence. To illustrate this effect on a non-log-likelihood function, we use BHHH on our running ellipse example. Figure 9 shows that the algorithms failed to solve an easy optimisation problem. In addition to the slower convergence to the minimum, it becomes unstable at the minimum. We also note that the method did not perform any dynamic rescaling (comparing to the Figure 8b) as it is following the gradient along with the ellipse geometry.

3.3 Mass tensor molecular dynamics

Mass Tensor Molecular Dynamics (MTMD) preconditioning is an efficient sampling method which uses generalised atomic masses [3]. The efficiency of molecular dynamics (MD) simulation is governed by the choice of the timestep. In some molecular systems such as liquid water, the appropriate timestep range from picosecond which can slow down the simulation significantly. MTMD alleviates the time-scale problem to some extent by taking advantage of the extra degree of freedom associated with the choice of atomic masses. MTMD makes the phase space nearly isotropic which leads to enhanced sampling. Consider the classical Hamiltonian for a system of N atoms

$$H_0(q, p) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \frac{p_i^2}{m_i} + U(q), \quad (3.17)$$

where m , q , and p are vectors of dimension N , denoting atomic masses, positions, and momenta respectively. $U(q)$ represents the potential energy function [60], or the Kohn-Sham total energy [42, 11]. Bennett [3] introduced the generalised Hamiltonian in the form

$$H_0(q, p) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} p_i M_{ij}^{-1}(q) p_j + U(q), \quad (3.18)$$

where M is a positive definite, symmetric matrix which stores the atomic mass at the positions q . We can define the canonical distribution in configuration space by

$$\rho(q) = \frac{\int dp \exp(-\beta H)}{\int dq dp \exp(-\beta H)}, \quad (3.19)$$

where $\beta = 1/k_B T$ and T is the temperature. If we substitute Eq. 3.18 in Eq. 3.19, we obtain

$$\rho(q) = \frac{|M(q)|^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-\beta U(q))}{\int dq |M(q)|^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-\beta U(q))}. \quad (3.20)$$

Therefore, we only need to find $M(q)$ such that it is independent of q in order to make $\rho(q)$ agree with original Hamiltonian. One way to choose M that satisfies the above conditions is

$$M \approx \mathcal{H} \times c(q), \quad (3.21)$$

where \mathcal{H} is the Hessian matrix and it's given by

$$\mathcal{H}_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2 U(q)}{\partial q_i \partial q_j}, \quad (3.22)$$

and $c(q)$ is a scalar function to compensate for the q -dependence of $|\mathcal{H}|$. which is sparse, symmetric, and indefinite matrix. To construct a positive definite matrix, a simple way is to define

$$M = (\mathcal{H} + \epsilon I) \times c(q), \quad (3.23)$$

where $\epsilon > 0$ and I is identity matrix.

A more robust definition can be defined based on the eigenvalue decomposition of \mathcal{H} . We first diagonalise by orthogonal matrix P as

$$\mathcal{H} = P^T \Lambda P, \quad (3.24)$$

where Λ is diagonal matrix given by $\Lambda_{ij} = \lambda_i \delta_{ij}$. We define

$$M_0 = P^T f(\Lambda) P, \quad (3.25)$$

where $f(\lambda) = (\lambda^6 + \epsilon^6)^{\frac{1}{6}}$ is filtering function. As M_0 is positive definite, we can finally write M in the form

$$M = c_0 M_0, \quad (3.26)$$

where c_0 is given by

$$c_0 = \left(\frac{\alpha}{|M_0|} \right)^{\frac{1}{3N}}, \quad (3.27)$$

and α is an arbitrary normalisation factor which does not depend on q . Therefore, $\det(M) = \alpha$ holds for any q , for any choice of V_H and ϵ .

Computing the Hessian matrix can be computationally expensive, hence we can approximate it by its average over the canonical ensemble [43] as follows:

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j} \right\rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \quad (3.28)$$

where Z is partial fraction and N is the number of degrees of freedom. We use integration by parts with respect to q_j to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \\ &= \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \right]_{q_j=-\infty}^{q_j=\infty} \\ & - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_j} \left(\frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \right) \\ &= \beta \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_j} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \\ &= \beta \langle F_i F_j \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

where F_k represents the force applied to the k th degree of freedom. Therefore, the ensemble-averaged Hessian matrix is equivalent to the thermally averaged force covariance matrix scaled by the reciprocal temperature β .

Similarly, the thermodynamic perspective allows of to derive an approximation for the third-order derivative of potential energy [52]. To obtain the ensemble-averaged third-order term, we first write the average their-order derivative expression and perform integration by parts with respect to variables q_j and q_k

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j \partial q_k} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_k \dots dq_N \\ & \times \left(\beta^2 \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_j} \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_k} - \beta \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial q_j \partial q_k} \right) \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

Next, we take the first integral and perform integration by part with respect to q_i

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j \partial q_k} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_k \dots dq_N \beta \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \\
&\times \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial q_j \partial q_k} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z}.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.31}$$

Finally, we multiply the above equations by $\frac{1}{2}$ and sum them up to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_N \frac{\partial^3 U}{\partial q_i \partial q_j \partial q_k} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} \\
&= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_1 dq_2 \dots dq_i \dots dq_j \dots dq_k \dots dq_N \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_j} \\
&\times \frac{\partial U}{\partial q_k} \frac{e^{-\beta U}}{Z} = -\frac{\beta^2}{2} \langle F_i F_j F_k \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{3.32}$$

Thus, higher-order optimisation algorithms could use the above approximation to find local minima faster in non-convex optimization problems, by exploiting the third-order smoothness to escape non-degenerate saddle points more efficiently.

We now propose three optimisation algorithms that rescale the dynamics of systems according to the preconditioning mass matrix.

Mass preconditioning method (MassBAO)

In the introduction, we showed that using a naive canonical sampler could lead to a wasted computational effort due to extended sampling of the irrelevant intermediate basin. Preconditioning methods such as Ensemble Samplers with Affine Invariance [23] and Ensemble Quasi-Newton [34] improve sampling efficiency by rescaling dynamics through local covariance information calculated from multiple walkers.

Mass rescaling method, rescale the dynamical systems by adapting the mass matrix based on the Hessian information. Consider Langevin dynamics of the form

$$\begin{aligned} d\theta &= p dt, \\ dp &= -\nabla_{\theta} U(\theta) dt - \gamma p dt + \sqrt{\beta^{-1} 2\gamma} dW, \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

where θ represent the parameters, p is the momentum and $U(\theta)$ is the energy function. We propose a mass preconditioned Langevin dynamics using splitting methods as introduced in (2.2) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{B-step} : p_{t+1/2} &= p_t - \frac{h}{2} \nabla J(\theta_t), \\ \text{A-step} : \theta_{t+1/2} &= \theta_t + \frac{h}{2} p_{t+1/2}, \\ \text{O-step} : p_{t+1} &= \alpha P_{t+1/2} + \sqrt{\tau(1-\alpha^2)} R_n, \text{ where } \alpha = e^{-\gamma h}, \\ \theta_{t+1} &= \theta_{t+1/2} - \frac{h}{2} M^{-1} \nabla J(\theta_t) + M^{1/2} R_t, \end{aligned} \quad (3.34)$$

where $c = e^{-\gamma h}$ and M represent the preconditioned mass matrix which can be obtained by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H} &= p^T \Lambda P \\ M_0 &= P^T f(\Lambda) P \\ M &= \left(\frac{\alpha}{|M_0|} \right)^{\frac{1}{3N}} M_0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.35)$$

In which the filter function $f(\lambda) = (\lambda^d + \epsilon^d)^{\frac{1}{d}}$ can ensure the matrix M is positive definite if d is even. We refer to this method as the ‘‘MassBAO’’ method.

One way to improve the efficiency of this algorithm by only computing the preconditioning matrix after k iteration similar to ensemble samplers algorithm in [34]. In fact, the idea of rescaling infrequently has become popular in the machine learning application under the name of ‘‘scheduling’’ techniques.

However performing MassBAO preconditioning becomes intractable in high-dimensional settings such as deep neural networks. In the next section, we propose a preconditioning Langevin dynamic method which is computationally cheap and suitable for training a deep neural network.

3.4 Preconditioned adaptive Langevin dynamics (PAL)

Inspired by adaptive timestepping method such as AdaGrad, AdaDelta and Adam, we propose *preconditioned adaptive underdamped Langevin dynamics* (PAL) which uses a different stepsize for every parameter and dynamically adjusts them using the gradient information. As we discussed in subsection 2.1, adaptive methods such as AdaGrad rescale the gradient values by the diagonal approximation of Hessian. To rescale the gradient we adjust the timestep that is multiplied by the gradient vector as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{t+1} &= \theta_t + \eta p_t, \\ p_{t+1} &= p_t + G(\theta_t)\hat{\eta} - \eta\gamma p_t + \sqrt{2\gamma\tau}dW_t, \\ \hat{\eta} &= \eta(D_t^{-1/2} + \epsilon I),\end{aligned}\tag{3.36}$$

where $\hat{\eta}$ is vector of timesteps for each parameter which is updated at each iteration, $D_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a diagonal matrix of exponentially decayed squared gradients

$$D_t = \begin{cases} \Psi_1 & t = 1 \\ \rho\Psi_t + (1 - \rho)D_{t-1} & t > 1 \end{cases}$$

and $\Psi_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is diagonal matrix of squared of gradient at timestep t defined as

$$\Psi_t = \begin{bmatrix} g_{t,1}^2 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & g_{t,2}^2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & g_{t,d}^2 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $g_{t,i}$ represent the gradient with respect to θ_i . PAL is a powerful optimisation method which combines the exploration aspect of thermodynamics-based methods and individual timestepping of adaptive gradient-based methods. Figure 10 illustrates the relationship between the optimisation methods discussed in section 2 and PAL.

Figure 10: Relation between PAL and other optimisation algorithms. Red squares represent thermodynamics-based and blue squares are gradient-based methods.

Another type of adaptivity is methods that try to control against gradient noise. Adaptive Langevin dynamics (AdL) [17, 27, 38, 57] is an underdamped Langevin method to overcome the gradient noise in constant temperature molecular dynamic simulation by replacing the friction by a dynamical variable which is adjusted through Nosé-Hoover thermostat algorithm [50]. AdL has shown promising results in Bayesian sampling [17, 27] as well as optimisation problems such as training deep neural networks [33].

We conjecture that the combination of Nosé-Hoover thermostat and adaptive timestepping would be a powerful method for training deep neural networks, although we do not discuss this approach here.

4 Diffusion analysis of statistical models

If we consider parameters of the model as molecules and optimisation process as molecular diffusion, we could model the convergence of optimisation as a diffusion process and evaluate its rate as *diffusion coefficient*. The inspiration comes from the work on diffusion in rugged energy landscape by Zwanzig [70] which we briefly describe here. Following that, we introduce a simple method to evaluate the convergence rate quantitatively.

4.1 Diffusion in a rough potential

Zwanzig derived an expression for the diffusion coefficient of rough one-dimensional potential by analysis of the mean first passage time under some assumptions [70].

The roughness of potential seems to slow down the diffusion at low temperature, especially when the fluctuation in the potential has a Gaussian distribution. Let us consider an arbitrary rough potential (Figure 11)

$$U(x) = x^2 + 0.02(\cos(133x) + \sin(50x)),$$

where the scalar 0.02 determines the measure of roughness. We can assume that at high temperature, particles can escape these barriers and the diffusion should be essentially unaffected by the small barriers. However, at low temperatures, particles don't have enough energy to cross over the barriers and as a result, their diffusion will be hampered.

Figure 11: A rough potential landscape with Gaussian fluctuation (from [70]).

We can describe the Brownian motion or diffusion of $U(x)$ by Smoluchowski equations to determine the time t dependence of the probability density $\rho(x, t)$ such that

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial J}{\partial x}, \quad (4.1)$$

$$J = -De^{-\beta U(x)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} e^{\beta U(x)} \rho, \quad (4.2)$$

where the top equation is known as *Fick's First Law* which is equivalent to Fokker-Planck equation for Brownian motion. J denotes the current density (flux), D represents diffusion coefficient, and $\beta = 1/k_B T$ is reciprocal temperature scaled by Boltzmann constant. The solution to the above equation is straightforward for smooth functions, while for rough potential, the approximate solution can be provided using mean first passage time (mfpt).

Zwanzig presented an approach to approximate the diffusion coefficient in cases where the potential landscape is rough. The expression replaces the original diffusion coefficient D by an effective diffusion coefficient denoted by D^* which is strongly dependent on temperature.

$$D_{\text{eff}} = \frac{D_0}{\langle e^{\beta U} \rangle \langle e^{-\beta U} \rangle}, \quad (4.3)$$

where D_0 represents the diffusion coefficient on the smooth potential, $\beta = 1/k_B T$ and $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the spatial, local average used to smooth the rough potential.

The preceding discussion was for one-dimensional diffusion (There seems to be no easy generalisation of the approach to a higher dimension). We conjecture that an analogous phenomena occurs in the high dimensional rough landscape. To estimate the diffusion coefficient, we use Einstein self-diffusion coefficient relation which relates the diffusion to the mean square displacement of particles. According to Einstein, the self-diffusivity is expressed by

$$D \equiv \frac{1}{2d} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle [r(t_0 + t) - r(t)]^2 \rangle}{t}. \quad (4.4)$$

To derive the above relation, we start with the pure stochastic diffusion equation for a one-dimensional setting

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \sigma^2 dW. \quad (4.5)$$

Then, we write the Fokker-Planck equation for the probability density of $\rho(x, t)$ to describe the time evolution of velocity of x

$$\frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial x^2}, \quad (4.6)$$

where D denotes the diffusion coefficient. The solution to the above equation is

$$\rho(x, t) = \frac{N}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{4Dt}}, \quad (4.7)$$

which represents a Gaussian distribution with mean $\mu = 0$ and variance $\sigma^2 = 2Dt$ which is also referred to as Brownian motion. The first moment vanishes and the second moment is obtained by

$$\langle x^2 \rangle = 2Dt, \quad (4.8)$$

which is equivalent Eq.4.4 in one-dimension.

We use the idea of diffusion in a rough potential and the Einstein diffusion coefficient equation to analyse the diffusion of an optimisation algorithm in high-dimensional settings.

If we consider a statistical model with d degrees of freedom, and denote the displacement of parameters at each timestep t by $\Delta\theta_t$, the diffusion coefficient can be approximated by

$$D \equiv \frac{1}{2d} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^T (\Delta\theta_i)^2}{T}, \quad (4.9)$$

where T is total number of steps.

5 Numerical studies

Our emphasis in the previous sections has been on studying various sampling and optimisation methods. In particular, we discussed the potential of thermodynamics-based approaches for sampling and optimisation tasks. In section 1, we briefly discussed the challenges in sampling a target distribution with an ill-conditioned landscape (Figure 1). To alleviate this problem, various preconditioning sampling methods were reviewed in section 3. Further, we proposed a novel preconditioned method (MassBAO) which rescales the dynamics by a mass matrix to improve the efficiency of sampling in ill-conditioned landscapes. In this section we evaluate the performance of our method in the challenging sampling task of Rosenbrock distribution (“banana” distribution). We show how MassBAO outperforms widely used sampling algorithms by considering different metrics.

In section 4 we introduced a diffusion-based technique to evaluate the exploration of sampling and optimisation algorithm. We show that the diffusion coefficient is correlated by the exploration rate in parameter space which can be enhanced by increasing the temperature. Additionally, we use diffusion analysis to explain the convergence rate of various deep neural networks.

In section 2, the most common optimisation algorithms in high-dimensional were discussed. In particular, gradient-based algorithms for training deep neural networks. We motivated using thermodynamics-biased approaches to enhance exploration in highly nonconvex and high-dimensional landscapes and showed that gradient-based algorithm can be thought of as a special case of thermodynamics-approaches where the temperature is set to zero. Moreover, we introduced an adaptive timestepping Langevin dynamics methods (PAL) which can be very efficient in the high-dimensional setting, in particular training deep neural network where the features are sparse and infrequent. We observe that PAL outperforms the state-of-the-art optimisation algorithms in a popular spiral data classification tasks as well as real-world challenging molecular states classification.

5.1 Sampling Rosenbrock using MassBAO

In this subsection, we compare the performance of popular sampling methods such as MH and HMC with our proposed preconditioned method (MassBAO). In particular, we focus on sampling Rosenbrock distribution as a challenging sampling task because its density concentrated on a lower-dimensional subspace.

The hyperparameters are constant throughout these experiments. For MassBAO, we chose $\gamma = 0.9$, $\alpha = 1$, $\epsilon = 1$, $d = 2$ and $\beta \in [10, 100]$, for MH $h = 0.1$ and for HMC $h = 0.01$. We note that the values for $\gamma = 0.9$ and $d = 2$ are optimal for a wide range of problems, while α and ϵ may required a minimal tuning for an optimal performance in a problem. As a rule of thumb, one can typically set $\alpha = 1$ and $\epsilon \in [0.01, 1]$. The reciprocal temperature β governs the exploration rate of the algorithm and can be chosen arbitrarily. We observed that the optimal values for beta are between 1 and 10^2 in this problem. We gauge the performance of MassBAO in a challenging sampling task followed by an optimisation task. We adopt three metrics to compare the performance of each sampling algorithm:

1. The distance between samples mean and the true mean $d_{\text{mean}} \equiv \|\mu_{\text{inf}} - \mu_{\text{true}}\|$,
2. The distance between sample covariance and true covariance
 $d_{\text{cov}} \equiv (\text{Tr}((\Sigma_{\text{inf}} - \Sigma_{\text{true}})(\Sigma_{\text{inf}} - \Sigma_{\text{true}})^T))^{1/2}$,
3. Integrated auto-correlation time to quantify the correlation between samples.

We consider a two-dimensional Rosenbrock density distribution as the target density. In two dimensions $[x, y] = q \in \mathbb{R}^2$ we have $\rho(x, y) \propto \exp(-U(x, y))$ such that

$$U(x, y) = (1 - x)^2 + 4(2y - x^2)^2. \quad (5.1)$$

The energy function is shown in the Figure 12.

Figure 12: Rosenbrock potential function as the target example **(a)**, starting points for sampling **(b)**.

As we can see from the Figure 12a, the distribution defined by the Rosenbrock energy function has a strong curvature that can challenge sampling algorithms to travel around the space.

We select 40 starting points randomly drawn from a uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(-10, 10)$ (Figure 12b) and perform sampling over different values of hyperparameters. For each starting point, we run 20 trials and report the average over trials. We let each trial runs for a total number of sampling from $N_{\text{samples}} = 10^3$ to $N_{\text{samples}} = 10^4$.

In Figure 13 we display the performance of MassBAO, MH and HMC algorithms. We observe that MassBAO performs significantly better and achieves the lowest sampling mean error. We see that despite the poor performance in estimating the mean, HMC achieves that lower covariance error (Figure 13b). This is because HMC fails to explore the landscape due to the small stepsize when the starting points are far away from the basin where the mass is concentrated (banana shape basin). We note that larger stepsizes lead to instability of HMC because the value of gradient becomes very large for some starting positions. By contrast, MassBAO rescales the dynamic and successfully samples the distribution.

Figure 13: Plots of convergence to the target distribution’s statistics such as mean and covariance, as well as integrated autocorrelation time and cpu execution time. By inspection, we observe that massBAO reaches more accurate inference than other samplers. The MH converges faster with the cost being inaccurate samples.

To estimate Integrated Autocorrelation Time (IAT), we used the EMCEE [23] python library. However, as the chain lengths were not long enough, the estimation may not be very accurate. In general HMC and MH have a lower IAT (Figure 13c). This is because in most initial conditions, they failed to samples the target density and they randomly generate samples which leads to a faster decorrelation.

It can be seen that the computational cost of MassBAO is higher and grows faster than MH and HMC. We suggest a few ways to enhance the computational efficiency of MassBAO:

1. Estimate the Hessian using the gradient as we show in section 3.3 Eq. 3.29,
2. Compute the eigen-decomposition infrequently,
3. Estimate the n largest eigenvalues and use them as an approximation,
4. Perform preconditioning every k steps.

Surprisingly, we can see from Figure 13 that applying preconditioning every 10 steps is very efficient and even more accurate than every step preconditioning. We initially suspected that the improvement was due to ABO splitting scheme and mass preconditioning gives the illusion of rescaling dynamic. We investigated this by comparing the K -step MassBAO and Langevin dynamics with ABOA splitting scheme. The observe that ABOA performs much worse than the other methods (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Comparison of ABOA methods with K -step MassBAO, MassBAO, MH and HMC.

In summary, MassBAO sampled the target distribution more accurately than the MH and HMC algorithms by rescaling the landscape and enhanced exploration through temperature.

5.2 Machine learning applications

In subsection 3.4 we introduce an adaptive Langevin dynamics (PAL) for high-dimensional optimisation. In particular, PAL can be very powerful methods for training deep neural network by handling sparsity of data and features. We first compare the performance of PAL with a non-adaptive Langevin scheme and Adam optimiser on 3-turn spiral data. We chose Adam because it is the most widely used optimisation algorithm for deep neural network training and it outperforms SGD, SGD-M, AdaGrad and AdaDelta in spiral data classification task. We chose the optimal set of hyperparameters for Adam such that the algorithm remain stable during training. In Figure 16c we see that Adam converges faster than SGD-M and increasing the learning rate causes spikes in the test loss and instability in the training process. We note that the values $\beta_1 = 0.99$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$ of Adam are standard values and they are not usually tuned [29].

In Figure 15 we see that PAL achieves a good classification accuracy after 300 steps and reached a good minimum after 500 steps, while Adam and non-adaptive Langevin method achieved high accuracy in 1,500 steps (Figure 16).

(c) Test Loss Comparison for Adam and SGD-M

Figure 16: Convergence rate for PAL (with $\gamma = 0.9$, $\tau = 1e - 6$ and $\eta = 0.01$), Adam (with $\eta = 0.01$, $\beta_1 = 0.99$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$) and non-adaptive Langevin (with $\gamma = 0.9$, $\tau = 1e - 6$ and $\eta = 0.01$).

Figure 15: Comparison of classifier for a 500-node SHLP on 4-turn spiral data generated by PAL (top row) vs Adam (middle row) and non-adaptive Langevin dynamic (bottom row). We display classification results by yellow and blue shades such that yellow and blue color represent high prediction accuracy and pinkish color represent low confidence in classification. By inspection, we can see PAL achieves a high accuracy with high confidence while Adam and non-adaptive LD are almost 50% confident in their classification by 500 steps.

Bovine pancreatic trypsin inhibitor (BPTI)

Training neural networks on sparse and unbalanced data could be difficult, in particular, when the classes have very similar characteristics. One challenging aspect of the BPTI dataset is sparsity of the data and close similarities between states. In order to make the dataset balanced, one can use “data augmentation” techniques to generate more data by small perturbation to the current dataset. We simply choose 500 randomly selected datapoint from each class to create a balance dataset. We choose 100 samples for testing and 400 for training. We note that for some rare state, less than 400 training samples are available. We choose a 500-node single hidden layer perceptron (SHLP) with ReLU activation function for hidden layer and Softmax activation for the output layer. We chose Cross Entropy as the loss function

$$J(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [y_n \log \hat{y}_n + (1 - y_n) \log(1 - \hat{y}_n)], \quad (5.2)$$

where $\hat{y}_n \equiv g(\theta x_n) = 1/(1 + e^{-\theta \cdot x_n})$, with $g(z)$ the Softmax (logistic function) activation.

As we discussed in section 2, adaptive optimisation algorithms can deal with sparse data by adapting learning rate according to frequency of features. In subsection 2.2 we mentioned thermodynamics-based approaches can avoid over-fitting to the training samples while gradient-based methods such as Adam tends to over-fit parameters to the training data. We used PAL and Adam optimisation algorithm as the data is very sparse and ran 5 trials for each method and report the average performance in Figure 17. Adam starts to over-fit after 600 epochs while PAL test loss monotonically decreases (Figure 17a). Although the difference in accuracy is not very large, considering the complexity of the problem and number of classes and datapoint, PAL performs significantly better than Adam (Figure 17b). As we can see from Figure 17c, some states such as 2, 14, 17 and 19 are harder to classify compare to other classes. By comparing this Figure 17c and Figure 3, it is clear that this method classifies rare states with higher accuracy. This means that the features of rare states are more distinctive than more frequent states. We note that as both algorithms achieved similar accuracy, we only plotted the comparison of test and training accuracy for PAL method. To further improve the accuracy, one may wish to add more datapoints from the frequent states, but this would unbalance the dataset which could lead to a poor performance. To alleviate this problem, we suggest “curriculum leaning” techniques as training strategies which in principal introduce gradually more difficult samples which could enhance generalisation and convergence of neural networks training.

(a) Test Loss

(b) Test Accuracy

(c) Test and Training Accuracy for PAL

Figure 17: Comparing performance of PAL and Adam on BPTI protein structure classification task. **a** shows the test loss during training. We can see Adam starts to over-fit after 600 epochs while PAL test loss monotonically decreases. **b** displays PAL has consistently higher test accuracy in the last 400 epochs and **c** is the final PAL classification accuracy for each state.

5.3 Diffusion coefficient

As we discussed in section 4, the exploration and convergence of sampling and optimisation algorithms can be analysed by their diffusion coefficient. To illustrate this, we estimate the dynamic exploration rate by looking at the parameter trajectory and the rate they spread out in space. A good example to show this effect is the double-well potential as it allows us to count the number of crossing between barriers easily. In Figure (18) we see the effect of increasing temperature on the number of barrier crossings (we use sign flip as a mean to detect barrier crossing) and estimated underlying distribution. At low temperature ($\tau = 0.1$) the ABO method fails to uncover the target distribution (Figure 18a) while by increasing temperature to $\tau = 10$ it manages to estimate the double-well potential accurately (Figure 18b). We use Eq. 4.9 to estimate the diffusion coefficient for parameters.

Figure 18c and 18d show that barrier crossings and diffusion coefficients both increase as temperature increases. If we consider the analogy of a physical system, the diffusion of particles in the space increases as temperature grows. Similarly, the movement of parameters within barriers becomes more frequent as the temperature increases.

Deeper neural networks tend to generalise better than shallow networks. [18] showed there is a class of functions in \mathbb{R}^d that are not expressible by a neural network with 2 hidden layers, while a deep neural network with 3 hidden layers can express those functions. Moreover, deeper neural networks converge faster to a good minimum compared to shallower deep neural networks. However, training deeper neural networks is harder due to the phenomena called “vanishing gradient” and “exploding gradient” where the gradient of inner layers becomes infinitesimally small or very large.

We conjecture that the reason deeper networks converge faster is that the parameters need to travel a shorter in space than the parameter displacement in shallower deep networks. To investigate this, we trained 5 neural networks with different number of layers but the same number of parameters. For brevity, we denote them as “N-HLP” where N denotes the number of hidden layers and HLP represents the hidden layer perceptron. To highlight the difference between various architecture, we chose “3-turn spiral” data classification tasks which we believe to have a loss landscape with many barriers. We used a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) as activation function for hidden layers, and sigmoidal activation for the output layer. Networks were training by the SGD-M algorithm with $\eta = 0.01$ and $\gamma = 0.9$. The spiral dataset that we use are generated by

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= at^p \cos(2bt^p \pi) + c\mathcal{N}(0, 1) \\ x_2 &= at^p \sin(2bt^p \pi) + c\mathcal{N}(0, 1). \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

To ensure that zero training loss is achieved at the global minima, we set $c = 0$. i.e. if the classifier can correctly classify all training data, it should be able to achieve 100% test accuracy as there is no additive noise to the data. We also generated enough training data to ensure the trained classifier learns the entire data manifold (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Spiral data generated by Eq. 5.3

(a) Estimated target distribution for $\tau = 0.1$

(b) Estimated target distribution for $\tau = 10$

(c) Number of barrier crossings against temperature

(d) Diffusion coefficient against temperature

Figure 18: Effect of temperature in exploration rate for double-well potential distribution. **a** shows that the sampling methods failed to uncover the full distribution due to the low temperature. In **b**, higher temperature led to an accurate distribution estimation. **c** and **d** indicated the relationship between temperature with number of barrier crossing and diffusion coefficient respectively.

In Figure 20a we display training loss against the number of steps for various deep neural networks with their corresponding diffusion coefficient as well as layer-wise diffusion coefficient which are estimated according to Eq. 4.9. We observe that deeper neural networks have a smaller diffusion coefficient and converge faster to a good minimum. This observation supports our hypothesis that the parameters in deeper neural networks are required to travel a shorter distance in the space to reach a good minimum. This could mean that as networks get deeper, the number of good minima in the vicinity of the initial points increases.

We can see that 3-HLP, 4-HLP and 5-HLP have similar diffusion coefficients and similar convergence rates. It is not clear why adding more hidden layers to the network does not improve the convergence rate. We hypothesis is that for a given problem, there is an optimal number of hidden layers that can express the underlying data distribution. This means that the need for deeper networks can be eliminated which could lead to an easier optimisation procedure. This observation is supported by the empirical study [69] that shows that in deeper neural networks, the parameters of the middle layers do not change during training, i.e. those layers are not “critical” and resetting their values to their initial conditions will not affect the performance after training. We can clearly see this in Figure 20b that the second layer has the highest diffusion coefficient while it decreases for deeper layers. In deep neural network architectures, i.e. more than 1 hidden layer, the diffusion coefficient for the last layer is near zero. This observation was empirically supported in [30] which shows that freezing the parameters of the last layer can enhance generalisation and increase convergence rate.

Figure 20: Comparison of diffusion coefficient for various deep neural networks. **a** displays that lower diffusion coefficient leads to a faster convergence and **b** shows that some layers tend to have higher diffusion coefficient.

Our observation could explain why using higher temperature for inner layers was advantageous and accelerated the convergence rate in [33].

Diffusion coefficient analysis could shed light on mysteries of neural networks training and help us understand the inner working of deep neural networks. It could be particularly useful to compare various deep neural network architecture and the performance of different optimisation algorithms.

6 Conclusion

In this thesis, we described challenges in sampling and optimisation tasks and discussed the potential of thermodynamic-based approaches. We presented a novel preconditioned thermodynamics sampling algorithm (MassBAO) which rescales the dynamic through a preconditioning mass matrix. We observed that MassBAO outperforms widely used sampling methods such as MH and HMC. We also proposed techniques to improve the computational efficiency of MassBAO. In particular, k-step MassBAO showed superior accuracy and computational cost compare to other methods.

We reviewed the state-of-the-arts optimisation algorithms in high-dimensional and showed that they can be thought as the special case of thermodynamics-based approaches with temperature set to zero. This relation allowed us to combine gradient-based approaches with thermodynamics-based schemes and develop a hybrid algorithm that starts by exploring the landscapes and converges when reaches a vicinity of a good minimum.

We also introduced a diffusion based technique to study optimisation schemes in high-dimensional settings. Our observations indicates diffusion coefficient can be a powerful tool to understand the training and underlying mechanism of deep neural networks. The experimental observations are supported by theoretical and empirical studies in the literature, which suggests the potential of using diffusion coefficient as a tool for unravelling phenomena in deep neural networks.

Additionally, we proposed a preconditioned adaptive Langevin dynamics (PAL) algorithm for training deep neural networks. We showed that it converges faster than non-adaptive Langevin dynamics and Adam optimiser on 3-turns spiral data. We compared our adaptive Langevin method method with Adam for training a neural networks for classifying the BPTI protein structure. We observed that Adam tends to overfit and perform poorly compared to PAL.

In terms of future directions for research, there are several experiments, test and challenges to be considered. The evaluation of MassBAO was limited to a 2 dimensional but challenging distribution. This showed that MassBAO can accelerate the convergence significantly compared to widely used sampling methods. We introduced an alternative computationally efficient MassBAO as “k-step MassBAO”, but the optimal value of k is unknown. It is natural to evaluate our method on variety of sampling tasks and study approximation techniques to improve the computational efficiency of MassBAO for sampling and optimisation tasks.

We observed that diffusion coefficient estimation can be use as a tool to analyse the training process of deep neural networks. To highlight the power of this technique, new experiments need to be done in different deep neural network architecture such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) on various benchmark datasets and optimisation algorithms.

Finally, we highlighted the power of our adaptive preconditioned Langevin dynamics (PAL) on challenging tasks of protein structure classification. Next, we need to evaluate this method on various types and deeper neural networks on benchmark datasets.

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